

Article: "Improved radiation expression profiling in blood by sequential application of sensitive and specific gene signatures"
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09553002.2021.1998709>

Zenodo Archive for "Improved radiation expression profiling by sequential application of sensitive and specific gene signatures"
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009007>

Usage of Machine-Learning Radiation Gene Signatures from: "Improved radiation expression profiling in blood by sequential application of sensitive and specific gene signatures"

Motivation

Combinations of expressed genes can discriminate radiation-exposed from normal control blood samples by machine learning (ML) based signatures (with 8–20% misclassification rates). These signatures can quantify therapeutically relevant as well as accidental radiation exposures. The prodromal symptoms of acute radiation syndrome (ARS) overlap those present in influenza and dengue fever infections. Surprisingly, these human radiation signatures misclassified gene expression profiles of virally infected samples as false positive exposures.

The ML radiation exposure models (or "gene signatures") derived in the study "Improved radiation expression profiling in blood by sequential application of sensitive and specific gene signatures" (Mucaki et al. 2021; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09553002.2021.1998709>) were utilized to investigate the effect of confounders, and derive signatures which mitigate confounder impact on signature accuracy. These ML models were derived using support-vector machines (SVMs), which are supervised learning models utilized in classification and regression analysis. This archive provides the ML models utilized in this manuscript (denoted as: M1-M20, KM1-KM7, SM1-SM5) as MATLAB formatted data (MAT files). The following documentation provides instructions on how to utilize these models to analyze your own test expression data sets.

Overview

This archive provides ML-derived radiation exposure models derived and/or utilized in Mucaki et al. (2021) as MAT files to be used by research groups. This document describes how to prepare external expression data sets to be tested by these radiation gene signatures, how to import the expression data and gene signature MAT files into MatLab, and how to utilize these models to perform traditional validation against the test dataset. It then explains how to read and understand the output of this test (i.e., how to determine if individuals were predicted irradiated or not).

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Implementation

Software Requirements

1. A License to and Installation of MatLab is required
 - a. Version of MatLab used in this study: "9.6.0.1174912 (R2019a) Update 5"
2. A License and Installation to the MatLab toolbox "Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox" is also required

Preparation of Test Expression Data

1. Expression data to be analysed by the ML radiation models must be structured as follows:
 - Rows: Individuals tested
 - Columns: Genes Analysed

Example:

Individuals	Label	GADD45A	DDB2	...
GSM29817	0	-1.20542	-0.88588	
GSM29822	0	-1.26734	-1.27788	
GSM29825	0	-0.76405	-0.99905	
GSM29828	0	-0.66447	-1.05176	
GSM29831	0	-0.57004	-1.13069	
GSM29834	0	-1.00947	-0.99208	
...	

2. The expression data to be tested must contain the expression for every gene present within the ML model being utilized in the same order. The column order must follow the order of genes for each signature (below). The software is intended to analyse a single signature with a single set of gene expression data which can be from the GEO datasets described in the paper, or from your own project (normalized; see below). Each signature is analysed separately.

Model	Required Gene Order
M1	DDB2 HSPD1 MAP4K4 GTF3A PCNA MDH2
M2	DDB2 GTF3A TNFRSF10B
M3	DDB2 CD8A TALDO1 PCNA EIF4G2 LCN2 CDKN1A PRKCH ENO1 PPM1D
M4	DDB2 CD8A TALDO1 PCNA LCN2 CDKN1A PRKCH ENO1 GTF3A IL2RB NINJ1 BAX TRIM22 PRKDC GADD45A MOAP1 ARPC1B LY9 LMO2 STX11 TPP2 CCNG1 GABARAP BCL2 GSS FTH1
M5	AEN BCL2

M6	RPS27L ZMAT3
M7	AEN ERCC1 BAX
M8	AEN TNFRSF10B
M9	BAX FDXR
M10	BAX FDXR XPC
M11	BAX DDB2
M12	BAX DDB2 SLC7A6
M13	RPS27L DDB2 ARL6IP1 TRIM32
M14	FDXR TRIM22 BAX XPC PHLDA3 TP53I3 MDM2 RPS27L ASTN2 SLC7A6 DDB2 FHL2 MAP4K4 TNFRSF10B CCDC90B IER5 GPX1 C12orf5 POLH ZMAT3 TRIAP1 TNFSF8 DRAM1 SESN1 ASCC3 MYC ACTA2 AEN GADD45A ARL6IP1 CDKN1A TMEM30A ISG20 PTMA PARP2 PPM1D GSS ARHGEF3 TP53TG1 ANXA4 ISCU FAS PVT1 BBC3 METAP1 CCNG1 PCNXL2 TRIM32 URI1 NME2 PHPT1 VWCE BCL2 PCNA POU2AF1 WNT3
M15	FDXR TRIM22 XPC PHLDA3 TP53I3 MDM2 RPS27L ASTN2 SLC7A6 DDB2 FHL2 MAP4K4 TNFRSF10B CCDC90B IER5 GPX1 C12orf5 POLH ZMAT3 TRIAP1 TNFSF8 DRAM1 SESN1 MYC ACTA2 AEN GADD45A ARL6IP1 CDKN1A TMEM30A ISG20 PTMA PARP2 PPM1D GSS ARHGEF3 TP53TG1 ANXA4 ISCU FAS PVT1 BBC3 METAP1 CCNG1 PCNXL2 TRIM32 URI1 NME2 PHPT1 VWCE BCL2 PCNA POU2AF1 WNT3
M16	FDXR TRIM22 BAX XPC PHLDA3 TP53I3 MDM2 RPS27L ASTN2 SLC7A6 DDB2 FHL2 MAP4K4 TNFRSF10B CCDC90B IER5 GPX1 C12orf5 POLH ZMAT3 TNFSF8 DRAM1 SESN1 ASCC3 MYC ACTA2 AEN GADD45A ARL6IP1 CDKN1A ISG20 PTMA PARP2 PPM1D GSS ARHGEF3 TP53TG1 ANXA4 ISCU FAS PVT1 BBC3 METAP1 CCNG1 PCNXL2 TRIM32 URI1 NME2 PHPT1 VWCE BCL2 PCNA POU2AF1 WNT3
M17	FDXR TRIM22 XPC PHLDA3 TP53I3 MDM2 RPS27L ASTN2 SLC7A6 DDB2 FHL2 MAP4K4 TNFRSF10B CCDC90B IER5 GPX1 C12orf5 POLH ZMAT3 TRIAP1 TNFSF8 DRAM1 SESN1 ASCC3 MYC ACTA2 AEN GADD45A ARL6IP1 CDKN1A ISG20 PTMA PARP2 PPM1D GSS ARHGEF3 TP53TG1 ANXA4 ISCU FAS PVT1 BBC3 METAP1 CCNG1 PCNXL2 TRIM32 URI1 NME2 PHPT1 VWCE BCL2 PCNA POU2AF1 WNT3
M18	FDXR TRIM22 BAX XPC PHLDA3 TP53I3 MDM2 RPS27L ASTN2 SLC7A6 DDB2 FHL2 MAP4K4 TNFRSF10B CCDC90B IER5 GPX1 C12orf5 POLH ZMAT3 TNFSF8 DRAM1 SESN1 ASCC3 MYC ACTA2 AEN GADD45A ARL6IP1 CDKN1A TMEM30A ISG20 PTMA PARP2 PPM1D GSS ARHGEF3 TP53TG1 ANXA4 ISCU FAS PVT1 BBC3 METAP1 CCNG1 PCNXL2 TRIM32 URI1 NME2 PHPT1 VWCE BCL2 PCNA POU2AF1 WNT3
M19	FDXR TRIM22 XPC PHLDA3 TP53I3 MDM2 RPS27L ASTN2 SLC7A6 DDB2 FHL2 MAP4K4 TNFRSF10B CCDC90B IER5 GPX1 C12orf5 POLH ZMAT3 TRIAP1 TNFSF8 DRAM1 SESN1 ASCC3 MYC ACTA2 AEN GADD45A ARL6IP1 CDKN1A TMEM30A ISG20 PTMA PARP2 PPM1D GSS ARHGEF3 TP53TG1 ANXA4 ISCU FAS PVT1 BBC3 METAP1 CCNG1 PCNXL2 TRIM32 URI1 NME2 PHPT1 VWCE BCL2 PCNA POU2AF1 WNT3
M20	FDXR TRIM22 BAX XPC PHLDA3 TP53I3 MDM2 RPS27L ASTN2 SLC7A6 DDB2 FHL2 MAP4K4 CCDC90B IER5 GPX1 C12orf5 POLH ZMAT3 TRIAP1 TNFSF8 DRAM1 SESN1 ASCC3 MYC ACTA2 AEN GADD45A ARL6IP1 CDKN1A TMEM30A ISG20 PTMA PARP2 PPM1D GSS ARHGEF3 TP53TG1 ANXA4 ISCU FAS PVT1 BBC3 METAP1 CCNG1 PCNXL2 TRIM32 URI1 NME2 PHPT1 VWCE BCL2 PCNA POU2AF1 WNT3
KM1	GADD45A DDB2

KM2	PPM1D DDB2 CCNF CDKN1A PCNA GADD45A PRKAB1 TOB1 TNFRSF10B MYC CCNB2 PTP4A1 BAX CCNA2 ATF3 LIG1 CCNG1 FHL2 PPP1R2 MBD4 RASGRP2 UBC NINJ1 TRIM22 IL2RB TP53BP1 PTPRCAP EEF1D PTPRE RAD23B EIF2B4 STX11 PTPN6 STK10 PSMD1 BTG3 MLH1 RNPEP HSPD1 UNG PTPRC PTPRA BCL2 GSS SH3BP5 TPP2 IDH3B CCNH STK11 EIF4EBP2 HSPA4 FADS2 RPA3 GZMK ANXA4 ICAM1 PPIID LMO2 PPIE NUDT1 FUS POLR2A LY9 RPA1 PTS TNFRSF4 RPA2 PSMD8 GCDH MAN2C1 PTPN2 RUVBL1 ATP5H GK CD79B MAP4K4 POLE3 PRKCH AKT2 MOAP1 CCNG2 ALDOA SRD5A1 HAT1 XRCC1 EIF2S3 RAD1 UBE2A ZFP36L1 CD8A TALDO1 GPX4 SSBP2 ERCC3 ATP50 PEPD EIF4G2 ACO2 HEXB UBE3A ARPC1A PSMD10 PRCP PPIB ZNF337 CETN2 RPL29
KM3	DDB2 RAD17 PSMD9 LY9 PPIH PCNA MDH2 MOAP1 TP53BP1 PPM1D ATP5G1 BCL2L2 ENO2 PTP4A1 PSMD8 LIG1 FDPS OGDH CCNG1 PSMD1
KM4	DDB2 HSPD1 ICAM1 PTP4A1 GTF3A LY9
KM5	RAD17 TNFRSF10B PSMD9 LY9 PPIH PCNA ZNF337 MDH2 TP53BP1 PPM1D ZFP36L1 ATP5G1 ALDOA BCL2L2 ENO2 GADD45A PTP4A1 PSMD8 LIG1 ATP50 FDPS OGDH PSMD1
KM6	DDB2 PRKDC PRKCH IGJ
KM7	DDB2 PRKDC TPP2 PTPRE GADD45A
SM1	PDE7A FBXW7 CLCF1 ALB IDUA USP3 SLPI COASY MFAP4 LTBP1 VPS37B VEGFA IRAK3
SM2	PDE7A FBXW7 CLCF1 ALB IDUA USP3 SLPI COASY MFAP4 LTBP1 VPS37B VEGFA IRAK3 MZB1 DHH GRN AEBP1 CNPY3 NUCB1 RDH11 CXCL3 POFUT1 CST1 ARCN1 PLA2G12A ERAP2 GOLM1 B3GAT3 ADAMTS9 FKBP9 ALDH9A1 LY86 HARS2 PRSS21 RETN C1GALT1 MGAT2 FUCA1 TTC19 MANF LUM GALNT15 APOM NME1 ATMIN GPX4 POLL LY6H SMARCA2
SM3	TRIM24 TOR1A GRN HP RBP4 PFN1 FN1
SM4	XCL1 CDC40 PTGS2 DHX8 NENF PTX3 WNT1 CTSW TINF2 AOA H VPS51 TOR1A HINT2 CRTAP SUCLG1 TF EDEM2 LAMA5 AGPS TFPI WFDC2 SRGN SIL1 PPOX AMY2A NUBPL GARS LRPAP1 VPS37B PNP C3orf58 HP SPOCK2 NME1 GRN TRIM24 MRPL34 SRP14 THOC3 RNASE6 RBP4 MSRB2 RNASET2 TGFBI PRDX4 GLA GLB1 PFN1 GDF15 VCAN TRIM28 TAGLN2 TIMP1 IPO9 CPVL MANBA CEP57 RNF146 PF4 RETN HCCS DPP7 RNASE2 QPCT AHSG CTSC LYZ B2M EMILIN2 STOML2 LCN2
SM5	TRIM24 IRAK3 PPP1CA MTX2 FBXW7 PFN1 SDHB CTSC MSRB2

3. Open MatLab

4. Import expression dataset into MatLab as a numeric matrix:

- a. Go to Home > Import Data (boxed command)

- b. Select file which contains your ordered gene expression data
 c. Under 'Output Type' drop-down menu, select 'numerical matrix'

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- d. Highlight the gene expression values of all data to be imported (DO NOT include patient identifiers, gene identifiers or outcome information)

	A	B	C	D	E
BuildingSVMXMLFilesS4					
Gene	...	Label	GADD45A	DDB2	
Text	...	Number	Number	Number	
	...	Label	GADD45A	DDB2	
GSM29817	...	0	-1.2054	-0.8859	
GSM29822	...	0	-1.2673	-1.2779	
GSM29825	...	0	-0.7641	-0.9990	
GSM29828	...	0	-0.6645	-1.0518	
GSM29831	...	0	-0.5700	-1.1307	
GSM29834	...	0	-1.0095	-0.9921	
GSM29784	...	0	-0.3692	-0.7038	
GSM29787	...	0	-0.6460	-0.6638	
GSM29793	...	0	-0.5784	-1.0167	
GSM29796	...	0	-0.4261	-1.1111	
...

- e. Click "Import Selection" on the top-right (see image after point 4c). The dataset will be imported to the Workspace in MatLab (see image below). A name will be automatically given to the imported data: it is suggested that the name be modified to something more specific.

5. Z-Score Normalize Expression Data using built-in MatLab function 'zscore':
 - a. Type the following command into the "Command Window":

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```
[output] = zscore(Input);
```


Import of ML-Derived Radiation Gene Signature (MAT file)

6. Download and Import MAT files from the Zenodo archive

- a. Download ML model MAT files ("Radiation_Model_MAT_Files.zip") from the Zenodo Archive:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009007>
- b. Decompress the Zip file using your preferred decompression program
- c. Move MAT files to your working directory
- d. Double-click the MAT file for the ML model you plan on using (e.g., "IJRB_SVM_Model_M1" contains the 'M1' gene signature). An import wizard will then open:

- e. Click "Finish". The model should now appear in your workspace.

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Name	Value
ImportedTestData	110x2 double
NormalizedTestData	110x2 double
svmModelKM1	1x1 Classificatio

Performing Traditional Validation on Test Dataset with ML Model

7. Use model to test normalized test dataset:

a. Type the following command into the "Command Window":

```
[predictions,hyperplane] = predict(svmModelKM1, NormalizedTestData);
```


After the command is entered, two new data tables will appear under the Workspace: 'predictions' and 'hyperplane' (name will change if output names are modified within the input command). To view these results, double-click their names in the Workspace.

b. 'predictions' will contain the predictions made by the selected model as a binary: those predicted irradiated are assigned a '1', while those predicted to be non-irradiated are assigned a '0'. Row order matches the input (i.e., the prediction for the individual whose expression data was in the first row will appear on the first row of the 'predictions' file).

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	1	2	3
1	0		
2	0		
3	0		
4	0		
5	0		
6	0		
7	0		
8	0		
9	0		
10	...		

Compare these predictions to the known exposure of the tested individuals to determine the accuracy of said predictions. Note that the prediction of a test sample that are near the decision threshold can change from run to run. It is therefore recommended that this test be rerun several times and the results averaged.

- c. 'hyperplane' presents the distance of the prediction of the tested SVM model against the hyperplane boundaries to separate samples into exposure classes by maximizing the distance between the separating hyperplanes and samples of each class.